

Deliverable

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D6.4-Short Movie

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P	Public	P
C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Abstract: The objective of the short movie was to offer fast information regarding the project aims, at the same time as offering the different accessibility services within the ImAc project.

Two videos have been created: Ethical considerations (<https://youtu.be/0BxrhAOmV4c>)

ImAc project (https://youtu.be/HuJPOUIY_EM)

Still other videos were produced for internal use of the project.

REVISION HISTORY

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	22-03-2019	Pilar Orero	UAB	First draft
0.2	29-03-2019	Pilar Orero	UAB	Final Version

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Statement of originality:

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Two videos were produced in ImAc early stage:

- a) Inform about the project ImAC and its objectives
- b) Inform on the Ethical Requirements for tests

This last video was generated for both internal and external use, since all partners testing with end users should understand and observe all Ethical Requirements obtained with the certificate. It is expected that at least one more video will be generated portraying ImAc developments as part of WP6 dissemination.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of this document

In this section we give a description of the first movies generated ad hoc for the ImAc project.

1.2. Status of this document

At the time of writing this document only two videos had been generated. The reason for this is that we are still testing how accessibility will be implemented. It is hoped that in the future another video will be created. A further problem is the fact that content used for tests has copyright, and we will need clearance to be able to make a video for public distribution.

Image 1. Romeo and Juliette subtitled

In image 1 we have the video produced during ImAc project from the Romeo and Juliette opera (<http://www.imac-project.eu/2018/02/12/imac-goes-to-the-opera-romeo-and-juliette-in-360o-uab/>). We are at present dealing with the memorandum of understanding with the owner of the opera production The Liceu Opera House in Barcelona. If this is cleared, we shall be able to include this and other video excerpts in the new ImAc video.

1.3. Relation with other WP2 and WP5 activities

The first video “Ethical Requirements” was produced to be ready for WP2 first tests to define user requirements. Also “Ethical Requirements” have been defined for the intermediate tests and testing taking place in the final stage of ImAc starting after the summer 2019.

2. VIDEOS

Two videos have been created, one to raise awareness of the ethical requirements, and one to give an overview of the first year of the project.

2.1. Ethical Requirements

The first video Ethical Content was ready at the very start of the project. The aim was:

- to secure all partners were aware of the Ethical Requirements in the project.

- to understand the ethical procedures
- to have a standard and common protocol for all tests

The video shows the different forms required to be filled in before testing, and to bring up the user needs regarding accessibility services, they may need to get both the information and consent forms. It also explained the need to gather a signature in case any test was filmed, or users were involved in any photograph. Finally the video shows the alternative ways to administer the forms, for vulnerable groups, that is with people with disabilities in the ImAc case. The video lasted 2 minutes and was subtitled.

Image 2. Frame of Ethic Requirements video

2.2. ImAc Video

The second video produced is the ImAc video (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HuJPOUIY_EM&feature=youtu.be). The video to date has had 85 views. It is published on Youtube and linked to the ImAc URL “Videos and Tutorials section” <http://www.imac-project.eu/immersive-corner/tutorials/>

The narrative is to point the project objectives before any results or recommendations are achieved. The video was subtitled in English.

Image 3. Frame of ImAc promo

The video wants to highlight the many ways to produce immersive environments from 3D to 360° videos. Through the different glasses needed for each interaction, the video starts

explaining how to view and enjoy immersive environments. It then explains ImAc objectives and the research and developments we are doing during the project. At this stage we are not in a position to offer definitive solutions to immersive accessibility, and we also have an issue regarding the public distribution of videos used for testing. The overall plan is to generate a video showing all the solutions in a simple and efficient way.

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